

INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING LINGUISTIC DISCIPLINES

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the actual topic of the use of interactive methods. Interactive teaching methods provide a solution to educational problems in various aspects. Interest in interactive methods is caused by the need to improve the modern system. The use of interactive methods makes it possible to organize independent cognitive activity of students during the lesson. Possession of interactive learning technology and its use in the educational process, including in Russian language lessons, will undoubtedly contribute to the development of students' qualities that correspond to the processes taking place today in life.*

Keywords: *training, interactive approach, exercise, task, developing technology, skills, abilities.*

Introduction

The main problem of the modern pedagogical process is the further improvement of the education system as a whole, aimed at developing the creative personality of the student. For the purposeful and systematic development of the intellect and creative thinking of students, it is necessary to apply modern pedagogical technologies in the classroom, aimed at activating and intensifying the activities of students.

As practice shows, the orientation of the transition to a new educational system to improve the education of students and its end result has necessitated the use of new teaching technologies and the choice of the most optimal teaching methods and techniques.

The proposed article contains instructions that reveal the content of the concept of interactive learning methods, the technological process and recommendations for the practical application of methods in the structure of the lesson.

The competence-based approach in organizing the educational process requires the teacher to change the learning process: its structure, forms of organization of activities, principles of interaction between subjects. And this means that priority in the work of the teacher is given to dialogic methods of communication, joint search for truth, and various creative activities. All this is realized using interactive teaching methods.

The teacher of a modern school carries out professional activities in a period of high rates of development of science and technology, information civilization, works in conditions where scientific knowledge becomes obsolete and is updated faster than students can assimilate within the framework of a specially organized learning process. Of particular relevance today are pedagogical approaches and technologies focused not so much on the assimilation of knowledge, skills and abilities by students, but on the creation of such pedagogical conditions that will enable each of them to understand, express and realize themselves.

In modern conditions, it is required to prepare the student for the rapid perception and processing of incoming information, to successfully display and use it.

Innovative processes in the field of education require a rethinking of the forms of the educational process as a control of the student's cognitive activity. This, in turn, determines the need to use new technologies that allow taking into account the individual characteristics of students. And today any methods capable of awakening the student's thought are declared non-traditional.

Research Methodology

I would like to dwell on interactive approaches to learning, which are understood as a certain type of student activity associated with the study of educational material during an interactive lesson. Methodists note that interactive learning is a special form of organizing cognitive activity, which implies very specific and predictable goals. Interactive methods are based on the principles of interaction, student activity, reliance on group experience, mandatory feedback. The basis of interactive approaches are interactive exercises and tasks that are performed by students. The main difference between interactive exercises and tasks from traditional ones is that they are aimed not only and not so much at consolidating already studied material, but at learning new things.

Modern pedagogy is rich in a variety of interactive approaches, among which are the following: creative tasks, work in small groups, educational games (role-playing, business and educational), the use of public resources (invitation of a specialist, excursions), extracurricular teaching methods (competitions, radio and newspapers, films, performances, exhibitions, performances, songs, fairy tales), warm-ups, study and consolidation of new material (interactive report, work with visual aids, video and audio materials, use of questions, dialogue), discussion of complex and debatable issues and problems, project lessons, talk show style discussion, debates, round table discussions, presentations, also problem-based learning.

The word "interactive" came from the English language, "inter" means among themselves, and "act" means to perform an action. In another way, "interactive" means to work hand in hand with someone, to be in dialogue with him.

Interactive technology:

- makes you think and create;
- teaches to analyze the received information;
- develops independent work of students;
- gives the opportunity to express their opinion, point of view in solving the problem;
- activates the work of students in a dialogue, group;
- jointly discuss the problem, find ways to solve it, learn from each other;
- teaches students to be responsible and cooperative.

In interactive learning, the student becomes a creative person. This means that the student ceases to be a consumer of knowledge, but learns to extract, construct, generalize knowledge, skills and abilities in the conditions of productive activity, i.e. works creatively.

The main element of interactive learning is developing technology.

So, the emerging technology:

- attracts students to the analysis of the stages of solving an educational problem, stimulates students to express their opinion, focuses on the use of different methods of action;

- teaches the development of attention, perception, memory, thinking, imagination, creative search work, work with educational text;

- maximum independence of students;

- develops a stable motivation for learning, for research work;
- forms the internal need of the individual for self-improvement;
- develops the creative abilities of students.

Principles of developing technology:

1. Increases students' knowledge, develops their creative level.
2. Develops intellectual skills, abilities, thanks to new technology.

There are three levels of developing technology that are used in the classroom:

Mandatory level.

Competent level.

creative level.

When performing multi-level tasks, students must successfully use logical operations by levels.

At the mandatory level, the following logical operations are used: highlight something, distinguish, know the features of something, give examples, supplement, select, work with words, insert, define, etc.

Logical operations of a competent level: observation, comparison, comparison, analysis, use of methods of induction and deduction.

The creative level includes such logical operations as the ability to plan, design, produce a synthesis, reflection (awareness of one's own experience is to write a review, review, summary), and broadcast knowledge.

In general, work on these levels:

- increases interest in the subject, has the development of creative abilities;
- teaches to analyze and synthesize, to make generalizations and conclusions;
- effective not only by the development of creative activity, but also by the mental function, culminating in the development of oral and written speech;
- enhances and deepens the knowledge of students, develops the intellectual level, teaches how to apply their knowledge in life.

Here are examples of tasks for three levels:

1. Mandatory level. Read the text, write out the SPP and determine their semantic relationships.

2. Competent level. Compose a discourse text on the topic: "The Internet in our life", using NGN with various types of clauses.

3. Creative level. Compose a text - research: "Young professionals", expressing their opinion with evaluative words: I think, I think, in my opinion, I'm sure, it seems to me.

When performing multi-level tasks, students think, compose, invent. Students compose texts of a different nature, such as: text - reasoning, text - narration, text - description, invent various dialogues, compose texts on topics, construct various diagrams and tables, compose stories with key words; write mini-essays, express their reasoning and opinions.

In conclusion, we note the positive results of this technology revealed in practice:

- improves the skills and abilities of speaking and writing;
- develops creativity;
- teaches to save time, organizes composure and attentiveness, develops mental activity;
- due to the compression of time, a "brainstorming" occurs, which is implemented at the expense of the intellectual level.

Conclusion

Of all the variety of pedagogical technologies of the humanistic direction, we mostly focused on the one that can be quite organically and easily integrated with traditional teaching, the classroom system. It is these technologies that are the main vectors of developmental learning. Here there is a qualitatively different approach of the teacher, which is not a way to decorate the lesson, to give students pleasure from the game techniques used, group forms of work, and frequent changes in activities. These are technologies with a very clear structure, which are based on developing and educational goals.

Under the conditions of interactive learning, students experience an increase in the accuracy of perception, mental performance, there is an intensive development of the intellectual and emotional properties of the individual: stability of attention, observation, the ability to analyze and summarize. Interactive learning contributes to the development of communication skills of students, helps to establish emotional contacts between them, activates teamwork, expands the range of educational opportunities.

An innovative approach to the educational process helps students to master new experiences based on the purposeful formation of creative and critical thinking, experience and tools for teaching and research activities, role-playing and simulation modeling.

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